

Enhancing Resiliency of Integrated Space-Air-Ground-Sea Networks with Renewable Energies: A Use Case After the 2023 Türkiye Earthquake

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Abstract—Natural disasters can have catastrophic consequences—a poignant example is the series of 7.7- and 7.6-magnitude earthquakes that devastated Türkiye on February 6, 2023. To limit the damage, it is essential to maintain the communications infrastructure to ensure individuals impacted by the disaster can receive critical information. The disastrous earthquakes in Türkiye have revealed the importance of considering communications and energy solutions together to build resilient and sustainable infrastructure. Thus, this paper proposes an integrated space-air-ground-sea network architecture that utilizes various communications and energy-enabling technologies. This study aims to contribute to the development of robust and sustainable disaster-response frameworks. In light of the Türkiye earthquakes, two methods for network management are proposed: the first aims to ensure sustainability in the pre-disaster phase and the second aims to maintain communications during the in-disaster phase. In these frameworks, communications technologies such as High Altitude Platform Station(s) (HAPS)—which are among the key enablers to unlock the potential of 6G networks—and energy technologies such as Renewable Energy Sources (RES), Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESSs), and Electric Vehicles (EVs) have been used as the prominent technologies. By simulating a case study, we demonstrate the performance of a proposed framework for providing network resiliency. The paper concludes with potential challenges and future directions to achieve a disaster-resilient network architecture solution.

Index Terms—6G networks, disaster relief, HAPS, sustainability, earthquake, renewable energy.

I. INTRODUCTION

On February 6, 2023, two powerful earthquakes struck Pazarçık and Elbistan, in Kahramanmaraş, Türkiye – with a magnitude unprecedented in recent history. The earthquakes, with magnitudes of 7.7 and 7.6, respectively, caused widespread damage in 11 provinces. The earthquakes have cost more than 48,000 lives and have destroyed more than 500,000 buildings, critical communications, and energy infrastructure, resulting in significant financial losses. According to the Turkish Information and Communication Technologies Authority, there are approximately 12 million mobile phone subscribers across the 11 provinces impacted by the earthquake, corresponding to approximately 14% of the entire country. The total damage in the telecommunications sector amounts to at least \$185 million, according to the Turkish Office of Strategy and Budget [1]. After the earthquake, satellite communications terminals, mobile Base Stations (BSs), emergency communication vehicles, and generators were delivered to the affected region.

The power outages in this region were the primary cause of the interruptions to mobile communication and internet services. While mobile BSs were sent to the region, limited service was delivered through generators that could merely provide an average of 3-4 hours of energy. As the power outages decreased, communication services began to be delivered for longer periods of time [1].

The series of devastating earthquakes has shown that energy and communication are among the most significant problems during natural disasters. Existing communication infrastructures and network equipment can be damaged in the event of a disaster or can be affected by power failures. As a result, the cellular network or Internet connection is unavailable and the central control authority is limited in its ability to receive timely information regarding the disaster area, further limiting the transmission of critical information [2]. In some instances, high-quality images need to be sent without interruption and with minimal latency for emergency response and life-saving treatments. Some existing energy and communications systems such as Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), satellite networks, Internet of Things (IoT), RES, EVs, etc. are used as solutions to this problem separately [3], [4]. However, instead of using these technologies individually, an integrated energy and communication structure should be considered in the development of disaster-resistant communication systems. Furthermore, this integrated network can be enhanced by novel technologies, such as HAPS from a communication perspective and BESS from an energy perspective. HAPS are promising candidates that provide numerous advantages such as coverage adaptability, endurance, rapid deployment, broadband capability, and low cost [5]. They also offer sustainable solutions for infrastructure damage, energy issues (e.g. power outages), and the restoration of damaged communication infrastructures.

In the light of above discussion, we propose the utilization of space-air-ground-sea networks with renewable energy to provide resilient and sustainable communications services during disasters. We consider integrated space-based networks (including satellite), air networks (including HAPS and UAV-based networks), ground networks (including Device-to-Device (D2D) communication), and sea-based networks as communication solutions, and RES (including wind turbines and solar panels), BESS, and EV as energy enablers. The disaster management life cycle consists of pre-disaster activities (mitigation and preparedness), response, and post-disaster recovery.

Taking into account these phases, for our integrated architecture, two methodologies are also proposed in the pre-disaster phase for sustainability and the in-disaster phase for communication resiliency.

II. CURRENT PROBLEMS OF TERRESTRIAL NETWORKS IN POST-EARTHQUAKE

A. Infrastructural Damage

Ensuring the continuity of communication systems' functionality is of critical importance in disaster situations. BS installations are frequently implemented on structures such as buildings and traffic lights, which are susceptible to the impact of disasters. Depending on the intensity of an earthquake, the backhaul links in BSs may also be damaged. For example, in the Türkiye earthquake, 25% of the existing BSs were disabled at time zero, and a significant amount of the fiber infrastructure became unusable¹. Also, while BSs on towers suffered relatively less damage, many of the BSs located on building tops were either destroyed or damaged. The primary issue was the BSs going out of service due to damage to the power grid. Considering the potential damage to both communication and energy infrastructure in the earthquake, it is crucial to develop integrated energy and communication-based alternative solution scenarios. Note that HAPS can play an active role, especially if the backhaul connection is damaged.

B. Energy Problems (Power Outage, Gas Transportation Problems)

During a disaster, power outages can occur due to various reasons such as the collapse of transformers, the toppling of transmission and distribution poles, and the breakage of power lines, etc. In such circumstances, the restoration of the power grid can be a time-consuming process. The endurance time of the generators is 3-4 hours; however, in the Türkiye earthquake, the fuel needed for generators to operate continuously was often not delivered on time due to challenging weather and field conditions [1]. As a consequence, the number of disabled BSs reached 50%, for some operators even on the second and third days after the disaster. In this regard, RES-supported sustainable Ground Base Station (GBS), RES-supported Eco Caravan systems, and the use of EVs as energy sources can provide significant contributions to the operation of terrestrial networks. In Vertical Heterogeneous Networks (VHetNets), HAPS also leverage the advantage of having a huge payload capacity. This enables them to utilize solar energy and batteries to sustain uninterrupted operation for months or even years [6]. Hence, it will become possible to prevent problems associated with power outages during disasters.

C. Restoring Communication

Restoring damaged communications infrastructure after a disaster or due to power supply problems is a vital problem that often takes a long time. The time taken to restore operations was also too long in Türkiye earthquake. The existing mobile BSs were

not enough, and mobile BSs were even brought in from different countries, and this process took days. As can also be seen from the Cloudflare statistics, the full capacity could already be reached again in one month after the earthquake². To this end, thanks to their strong Line-of-Sight (LoS) communications capability and a combination of radio frequency (RF) and Free-Space Optical Communication (FSO) for backhauling, HAPS nodes are able to provide communications services without the need for additional ground infrastructure. However, HAPS could have challenges, e.g; in terms of communication and sensitivity to environmental changes. Nevertheless, HAPS can be supported by various technologies and its effectiveness in reaching remote or densely populated disaster areas can be improved. By using technologies such as massive multiple-input multiple-output (mMIMO) and Intelligent Reflective Surfaces (IRS), HAPS can leverage precise beamforming and steering techniques. This enables HAPS to provide wireless connectivity over robust LoS connections, covering a radius of up to several hundred kilometers [7]. HAPS can also use the S-band to react more sensitively to changes in the environment.

III. PROPOSED SPACE-AIR-GROUND-SEA INTEGRATED NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

In this section, we propose a HAPS-supported architecture, which can be used as both Radio Access Network (RAN) and backhaul. HAPS mainly refers to airborne systems stationed at high altitudes, typically in the stratosphere, above traditional aviation airspace and can be in the form of drones, balloons, or airships. Fig. 1 shows the proposed integrated network architecture that combines many energy technologies like RES, BESSs and EVs and many communication technologies like Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellite systems, HAPS, UAVs, Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) etc at different layers, namely space, air, and terrestrial. In Fig. 1 the area in gray represents the disaster-struck zone. The shaded areas are as follows: (i) *A* represents RES supported sustainable GBS, which includes a BESS. (ii) *B* represents the RES-supported Eco Caravan system as using Movable and Deployable Resource Unit (MDRU). (iii) In *C*, an ISAC is indicated. (iv) *D* represents the D2D communication. (v) As shown in *E*, EVs can play an important role in disasters as a source of energy. In addition, EVs can be used as mobile relays. (vi) *F* represents the failed BSs and (vii) *G* represents the active BSs in the disaster. (viii) *H* represents seismic isolator-based solutions to improve the resistance of critical power system components such as transformers to seismic vibrations. (ix) *I* represents the sea-based networks. (x) *J* indicates a HAPS-based communication system. Some of the prominent communication and energy technology enablers used in the proposed architecture for the disaster scenarios are explained in the following subsections.

A. Communication Technology Enablers

Space-Based Networks can operate independently of terrestrial networks while providing a reliable and resilient communications

¹Online: <https://m-tod.org/operatorler-deprem-bolgesinde/>, Available: November 2023.

²Online: <https://blog.cloudflare.com/q1-2023-internet-disruption-summary/>, Available: November 2023.

Figure 1. Proposed integrated space-air-ground-sea network topology with energy and communication solutions.

infrastructure and emergency response support in remote or hard-to-reach areas. Satellites can play a crucial role in disaster response communication planning, particularly in the context of earthquakes, due to their wide coverage, resilience, and ability to provide connectivity in remote or damaged areas. Satellite networks can be used to establish temporary communication infrastructure in disaster-prone areas and communication channels between emergency responders, local communities, and other stakeholders. Rescue teams, government agencies, and relief organizations can use satellite connectivity to share vital information, coordinate resources, and efficiently manage rescue and relief operations. Satellite networks can also be used to share critical information such as maps, images, and video between emergency responders and command centers [8] and warn and disseminate important information to local communities. This information aids in identifying critical infrastructure damage, assessing the extent of the disaster, and guiding resource allocation and deployment.

Air-Based Networks contains novel technologies like HAPS and UAVs. HAPS can play a critical role in improving the resilience of integrated space-air-ground-sea networks during and after natural disasters such as earthquakes as shown in Fig. 1 *area J*. Some of the advantages of HAPS are: (i) Because of its surface area, it has the potential to generate almost its own energy with solar panels. (ii) A single HAPS can be an alternative to all damaged terrestrial BSs because it can provide a large coverage area. Here, a single HAPS can be perceived as a multi-sector (directional) BS. (iii) For almost all outdoor users, a direct LoS can be established that can com-

pen-
 (iv) Compared to satellites (e.g., Starlink), no additional intermediate devices (e.g., relays) are required. Moreover, satellites (e.g., LEO) can establish a LoS of maximum 6 minutes to any ground station. For this reason, thousands of satellites were launched to create a constellation, but HAPS can provide stable and continuous service because they do not make orbital movements. (v) They are very easy and quick to run in terms of logistics (especially useful in the first days after the earthquake, when it becomes impossible to reach the earthquake area by land). (vi) It is an important alternative not only on the RAN side, but also for the backhaul. A HAPS can easily forward all backhaul traffic to an unaffected area via links such as FSO/THz communication with a remote HAPS or ground station. During earthquakes, fiber optic lines can be damaged in the earthquake area, so some BSs may be out of service. (vii) It is not physically affected by weather events.

UAVs can also be a valuable tool for disaster communication planning and warning. It can be used to build temporary communications infrastructure in disaster-prone areas providing a versatile platform for gathering and disseminating critical information in disaster-prone areas and supports emergency response efforts. UAVs equipped with cameras or other sensors can provide real-time information about the extent of damage, the location of survivors, and other critical information that can be used to support emergency response efforts.

Ground-Based Networks consist of various components, including cellular networks, terrestrial Internet (that relies on physical cables, such as fiber optics or copper wires, to transmit data packets over long distances), and mobile ad hoc networks. Unlike air-based

networks, the topology of the ground-based networks is relatively stable and less mobile. In the event of a natural disaster, such as a hurricane, earthquake, or flood, the ground-based communication infrastructure can be severely damaged or destroyed as pointed out in Section II-A. This can make it difficult for emergency responders and survivors to communicate with each other. One way to overcome this challenge is to use D2D communication as shown in Fig. 1 *shaded area D*. D2D communication provides a decentralized and resilient communication solution in earthquake scenarios. It is especially useful in scenarios where the use of the power grid is inaccessible and the use of batteries for power is not possible. ISAC can also play a critical role in improving the resilience of integrated space-air-ground-sea networks with renewable energy, as shown in Fig. 1 *shaded area C* [9]. Firstly, the extent of the damage caused by an earthquake can be quickly estimated with ISAC. Sensors can be used to monitor the integrity of buildings and communication systems can be used to transmit this information in real time. Secondly, ISAC can be used to find survivors trapped in the rubble. Sensors can be used to detect movement and signs of life, while communication systems relay this information to rescue teams. Third, ISAC can provide real-time information about the situation on the ground, including the location of survivors, the extent of damage and the status of rescue efforts. Finally, ISAC can facilitate communication between response teams so that they can coordinate their efforts and share information in real-time. This can ensure that resources are allocated effectively and relief efforts are optimized.

Sea-Based Networks assumed critical significance during Türkiye earthquake, where traditional communication infrastructure in coastal provinces collapsed. In this network topology, various elements such as ships and unmanned surface vehicles can facilitate communication by leveraging UAVs, HAPS, and satellite technologies based on their respective locations as shown in Fig. 1 *shaded area I*. They can complement the proposed architecture by improving coverage and resiliency by offering diverse paths and reducing the risk of network congestion and outages. They can also facilitate interoperability between different types of networks (e.g., naval vessels, aircraft, and ground-based command & control centers) via standard or customizable protocols enabling seamless communication between different services and agencies.

B. Energy Technology Enablers

The importance of energy in the design and operation of future networks cannot be overstated, as global energy consumption is estimated to increase by 20% by 2030, driven by the growing number of subscribers, traffic demand, connected devices, and services driven by information and communication technologies [10]. Another critical factor is ensuring the resilience of power systems to maintain uninterrupted communications in the event of disasters, both during and after they occur. The term “power system resiliency” refers to the ability of an electrical power system to mitigate the magnitude and duration of disruptive events. Some of the possible solutions in this context are: (i) The introduction

of smart grids to replace centralized traditional grid infrastructures opens up the possibility of incorporating distributed generation units and microgrids based on renewable energies on a significant scale, and thus has the potential to play a decisive role in disaster scenarios. (ii) Ensuring a reliable power supply through the use of energy storage systems, such as BESS, is of paramount importance. (iii) The use of EV batteries in Vehicle to Load (V2L) applications is proving to be a viable approach. (iv) Implementing solutions based on seismic isolators is a promising approach to improve the seismic resilience of critical power system components to strong shaking.

The United Nations aims to achieve net-zero CO₂ emissions by 2050 to mitigate the impacts of climate change [11]. In order to achieve this goal, RES are a growing area of energy systems to enable decarbonization and sustainability policies. With the high penetration rate of RES such as wind and solar energy and the participation of RES-supported microgrids and RES-supported BSs, the energy system becomes more resilient to disasters. In addition, it will be possible to operate terrestrial communications systems for a much longer period of time during disasters. When considering air networks, the large surface area of HAPS, the lack of cooling systems required for communications and energy components, and the potential to meet nearly all power needs through the integration of Photovoltaic (PV) panels makes the use of RES in air-based networks feasible.

C. Integrated Approach

In this section, we provide some examples of the joint use of energy and communication enablers. In Fig. 1 *shaded area A*, it is proposed to install GBS towers in certain locations, especially in densely populated areas, and to support these GBS towers with BESSs. In this context, the GBS is aimed to produce its own energy with PV panels and wind turbines. The GBS can autonomously charge the BESS from the RES and in case of a power outage, it can utilize the stored energy from the BESS. Charging stations will also be available on the GBS towers, allowing the charging of multiple UAVs. UAVs can be directed to desired areas under the control of the Disaster Management Center, and UAVs with low battery levels can also be diverted to charging stations for recharging. UAV charging stations can be used not only in emergency situations, but also to support areas with high communication needs, agricultural or meteorological activities, observations, IoT applications, and various purposes such as communication with different sensor nodes. Note that MDRUs play an important role in the communication system and their energy requirements are mostly covered by diesel generators. MDRUs can be transformed into the Eco Caravan supported by RES, which is shown in Fig. 1 *shaded area B*. The aim is to have a portable vehicle equipped with a BESS, solar and wind energy. Thanks to EVs, the energy requirements of both GBS and MDRUs can be met. In addition, thanks to GBS and MDRUs with BESS, wireless power transmission technology for user devices can be evaluated in the event of a disaster.

In disasters, terrestrial communications can suffer severe damage. In Fig. 1 *area J*, a hybrid architecture combining satellite and

ground can be established in both S- and Ka-bands. In S-band, mobile handheld devices are supported, while in Ka-band Very Small Aperture Terminals (VSAT) (i.e., 60 cm circular polarisation) are required, which can be permanently installed or mounted on mobile platforms (e.g., vehicles, UAVs, etc.). During the earthquakes in Türkiye, the total affected area (11 provinces) is about 115,000 km² with a total of 12 million mobile subscribers [1]. Therefore, for the S-band simulations (Fig. 4 (a)), all 12 million mobile subscribers are randomly distributed in the area (for simplicity) and served by a single HAPS, 2-HAPS or 4-HAPS. In contrast, in the Ka-band simulations (Fig. 4 (b)), we assume that 1 million VSAT subscribers are randomly distributed in the same area and served by the same amount of HAPS network. In all simulations, the parameters of HAPS (e.g., transmit power, antenna gain, etc.) are used based on [13]. Air-to-ground channel characteristics (e.g., LoS probability, path loss, shadowing, atmospheric loss, etc.) and the receiver parameters (e.g., antenna gain, sensitivity, etc.) are also taken from [12]. From the extensive simulations, we can conclude that even a single HAPS could restore all communications in the region - and thus replace all failed ground BSs - as none of the users receive a signal lower than the receiver sensitivity. Nevertheless, by increasing the number of HAPS, we were able to improve quality-of-service (QoS) thanks to the 10-20 dB increase in received SNR by each HAPS. As expected, the performance deteriorates in the dense urban scenarios due to lower LoS probability and higher losses (e.g., shadowing, clutter losses, etc.) [12]. On the other hand, in Fig. 4 (b), we can observe an average 20 dB higher received power than in Fig. 4 (a) in all scenarios. This can be explained as follows. Although the path loss is greater in Ka-band, the antenna gain of the VSAT receiver can compensate for this and provide a higher QoS [13]. In summary, our simulation results show that even in the scenario in which all terrestrial BSs are deactivated, the communication needs in the earthquake-damaged region can be met with HAPS.

Our proposed methodologies combine terrestrial and HAPS technologies, but their objectives are different depending on the scenario considered. To compare our integrated hybrid methodologies with the primary communication enablers, Table I provides comparisons in terms of various key performance indicators (KPIs). According to the KPIs in Table 1, both *Methodology 1* and *Methodology 2* perform medium in terms of interoperability, latency and security but performs high in terms of bandwidth and scalability. Compared to *Methodology 2*, the proposed *Methodology 1* is better in terms of energy efficiency. However, *Methodology 2* provides better communication resilience.

V. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

The proposed architecture includes the use of different technologies, protocols, and strategies to ensure seamless communication and energy support in disaster scenarios. The challenges of coordinating the above elements include ensuring seamless interoperability, overcoming communication latency issues, and managing limited resources in a dynamic and often chaotic disaster environment. How

(a) Mobile handheld devices that operate in S-band.

(b) Very small (≈ 60 cm) aperture terminal users operate in Ka-band.

Figure 4. CDF of received power at the ground terminals for a HAPS-RAN communication in the whole affected region.

future networks can be managed to ensure seamless connectivity, interoperability, and efficient resource utilization must be considered as a future research direction. Note that there are some proposals for solving these problems in the field of integrated networks [14], [15], which could be used to find solutions. To achieve a disaster-resilient network architecture, some of the future solutions are as follows: **(i) Artificial Intelligence (AI) and blockchain networks:** Solutions that rely on AI-based techniques can be used to solve various disaster communication planning problems both in pre-disaster, in-disaster and post-disaster scenarios. In addition, AI together with blockchain frameworks can improve remote data protection and secure energy trading. **(ii) Cloud native deployments:** To improve network scalability and flexibility of networks in disaster zones, cloud-native deployments of network services can be used in space-air-ground-sea networks. This can also reduce development cycles, capital, and operational expenditures while enabling platforms to be open. Container orchestration tools like Kubernetes can help with cloud-native deployments. **(iii) Energy harvesting:** If the user's devices are able to use radio, solar or vibration energy from the environment, energy consumption constraints can be significantly reduced.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an integrated space-air-ground-sea network architecture is used, which uses various communication and energy-

Table I
COMPARISON OF COMMUNICATION ENABLERS FOR DIFFERENT KPIS IN EARTHQUAKE SCENARIOS WITH PROPOSED HYBRID METHODOLOGIES.

Technology \ KPIS	Satellite	HAPS	UAV	Terrestrial	D2D	Methodology 1	Methodology 2
Latency	High	Medium	Low	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
Bandwidth	High	High	Medium	Medium	Low	High	High
Resiliency	High	High	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium	High
Scalability	High	High	Medium	Medium	Medium	High	High
Security	High	High	Medium	High	Medium	Medium	Medium
Interoperability	Medium	Medium	Medium	High	Low	Medium	Medium
Cost-efficiency	Medium	High	Medium	Medium	Low	High	High
Energy efficiency	Medium	High	Medium	Low	High	High	Medium

enabling technologies, to improve resiliency and sustainability in disaster scenarios. The integrated communication network presented includes satellite, HAPS, UAV, and D2D technologies. In addition, the integration of various RESs (e.g., wind turbines and solar panels) together with innovative energy enablers (e.g., BESS and EVs) is proposed to ensure sustainable energy management in disaster situations. Specifically targeting the recent earthquakes in Türkiye, two network management methodologies are put forth. The performance of the proposed framework is validated through the simulation of a case study demonstrating the strength of HAPS communication in disaster areas. Future research and practical implementation in this direction holds great potential for the development of more resilient and sustainable disaster management strategies.

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